

The Influence of Competence and Personal Characteristics on Teacher Performance

Sovita Mustikasari¹, Nursaid, Abadi Sanosra², Nurul Qomariah³

^{1,2,3} Universitas Muhammadiyah Jember

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Corresponding Author:
Nurul Qomariah

ABSTRACT

Teachers are the spearhead in educating the nation's life. Improving teacher performance is absolutely necessary in achieving Indonesia Emas in 2045. This paper aims to examine the influence of competence and personal characteristics on teacher performance. The population in this study were all Junior High School teachers in the Central Region of Jember Regency, totaling 698 people. The number of samples was 254 teachers, calculated using the Slovin method. as many as 254 teachers, and selected using simple random sampling. Before data analysis was carried out, a prerequisite analysis test was first conducted which included reliability and validity tests. The data analysis methods used were ui alidity and reliability tests as well as direct hypothesis tests. The results showed that there was a positive and significant influence of competency variables on Performance. There was a positive and significant influence of personal characteristic variables on performance.

KEYWORDS: competence; personal characteristics; performance

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the most important aspects in the development of a nation. Education can form quality human resources, competitive, and contribute positively to the progress of the nation. Therefore, education must be provided with high standards and in accordance with the needs of the times. One of the factors that determines the quality of education is teacher performance (Mulyasa, 2011). Organizational performance usually depends on the performance of employees working in the organization. Teacher performance is the result of the application of teacher competence in carrying out their duties as educators. Teacher competence is the ability possessed and mastered by teachers to carry out their main tasks, functions, and responsibilities as educators. Teachers who have high competence and performance can provide effective, efficient, and meaningful education services for students. Conversely, teachers who have low competence and performance can reduce the quality of education and harm students. The competence possessed by employees will be able to improve performance. This is proven by the findings in research conducted by (Adam & Kamase, 2019; Amdani et al., 2019; Bahri et al., 2018; Basalamah, 2017; Friolina et al., 2017; Indiyarningsih et al., 2020; Manik & Syafrina, 2018; Mukhtar, 2018; Mustikawati & Qomariah, 2020; Nyoto et al., 2020; Pinca, 2015; Rande, 2016; Setiawati,

2017; Wasiman, 2020; Widyanto & Mersa, 2018; Wongso et al., 2020; Yamin & Ishak, 2018). Meanwhile, research stating that competence has no impact on performance was conducted by (Chandra et al., 2020; Utomo et al., 2019).

In addition to competence, one of the factors that can influence a teacher's success in teaching is personal characteristics. The character of a teacher is different from other professions, such as traders, technicians, and the military. Teachers in the sense of educators are different from tutors, trainers. Although, the teaching profession as an educator requires education and training, the teaching profession is not only related to hard skills, but more to soft skills (character) (Astutik & Priantono, 2020; Fatmah, 2017; Hajati et al., 2018; Sihombing et al., 2018).

Based on data obtained from the Jember Regency Education Office, in general, it was found that since 2019, teacher performance at Public Junior High Schools in Jember Regency has increased. However, the increase was not very significant. On the other hand, in 2020, the final score of the Teacher Performance Assessment actually decreased slightly. This decrease could have occurred due to many factors, including the Covid 19 pandemic that hit Indonesia. Based on this, a more in-depth study is needed to improve teacher performance at Public Junior High Schools throughout the Central Region of Jember Regency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance

According to Burhanudin, teacher performance is a reflection of the quality of work possessed by a teacher, which is manifested through the mastery and application of relevant competencies. This view emphasizes that teacher performance includes the ability to master and apply competencies in carrying out their duties and roles as educators. From the various definitions that have been explained, it can be concluded that teacher performance reflects the results or work achievements based on the ability to manage the teaching and learning process, which includes planning, implementing, evaluating learning, and building interpersonal relationships with students.

Competence

Therefore, in order to become an educator, one must have a minimum academic qualification of a Bachelor's or Diploma IV (S1/D-IV) that is relevant and master the competencies as a learning agent. The spirit of this article is to improve the competency of educators themselves, as well as to try to appreciate the teaching profession more. With this certification, it is hoped that the teaching profession will be more appreciated and can improve the quality of educators in Indonesia. This is done as a step so that educators become professional workers. Competence comes from the word competency (English) which means ability, capability, proficiency, qualification, eligibility, readiness, skill, and adequacy (Egan et al., 2004). According to (Qomariah, 2020), the definition of competence is something that describes a person's qualifications or abilities, both qualitatively and quantitatively. According to (Hutapea, 2008), competence is the ability to perform a set of tasks that require the integration of knowledge, skills, and attitudes, while competent is the ability to perform a role effectively in a context.

Personal Characteristics

Etymologically, character comes from charac or charassein, charatto which means stamp, fear, notch, stroke, carving. So character is a unique totality of an individual. Character is a form of organization of life feelings, recognition and will that are directed at a value system and expressed relatively consistently in achieving the values to be achieved. The character of a teacher is different from other professions, such as traders, technicians, and the military. Teachers as educators have fundamental differences with tutors or trainers. Although the role of teachers also requires education and training, the focus of this profession is not only on the development of technical skills (hard skills), but more on soft skills such as character. This is what makes the teaching profession unique compared to other professions. Soft skills that a teacher needs to have include sincerity, compassion, and idealism in educating, so that

they can shape students into individuals who are useful for religion, nation, state, family, and society (Subyantoro, 2009).

RESEARCH METHOD

This research can be classified as explanatory research. According to (Sugiyono, 2019), explanatory research is a research method that aims to explain the position of the variables studied and the influence between one variable and another, usually between the independent variable and the dependent variable. In this study, there are two independent variables, namely competence symbolized by X1, and personal characteristics symbolized by X2. There is one dependent variable, namely teacher performance symbolized by Y. In this study, the population to be taken is all sub-district employees in Jember Regency as many as 698 respondents. In this study, a sample was used by means of probability, namely simple random sampling. Of the total 698 respondents, the sample used using the Slovin formula was obtained as many as 261 respondents. The data analysis technique used in this study was using a hypothesis test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

This study distributed questionnaires to 261 respondents with a sampling technique using the Slovin formula. The answers to the questionnaire will be used to analyze employee characteristics that affect employee performance. Based on the results of the descriptive analysis based on gender, it can be seen that the respondents in this study were divided into 92 (36%) male respondents, and 162 (64%) female respondents. Based on descriptive analysis of respondents' ages, it was found that respondents aged 26-30 years old numbered 42 people (17%), aged 31-35 years old numbered 65 people (26%), aged 36-40 years old numbered 66 people (26%), aged 41-45 years old numbered 33 people (13%), aged 46-50 years old numbered 26 people (10%), and aged 51-55 years old numbered 22 people (9%). Meanwhile, analysis based on education level showed that respondents with a Bachelor's degree numbered 151 people (59%), while respondents with a Master's degree numbered 103 people (41%).

Validity Test Results

The validity test in this study was conducted by looking at the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value. If the AVE value is more than 0.5, it can be concluded that the indicator is valid.

Table 1. Validity Test Results

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Results
Competence (X1)	0.521	Valid
Personal Characteristics (X2)	0.639	Valid
Performance (Y)	0.570	Valid

Based on table 1. Then all variables in this study have AVE values above 0.5. So it can be concluded that all variables in this study are valid.

Reliability Test Results

A questionnaire is considered reliable if a person's answers to the questions given are consistent or stable across occasions. An indicator is considered reliable if it has a Cronbach's Alpha value of more than 0.6.

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Results
Competence (X1)	0.689	0.811	Reliable
Personal Characteristics (X2)	0.810	0.875	Reliable
Performance (Y)	0.748	0.841	Reliable

Based on table 2, it can be seen that all variables have a Cronbach's Alpha value of more than 0.6, which means that all variables in this study are reliable.

This direct influence hypothesis test was conducted to determine the impact of competence (X1) and personal characteristics (X2) on teacher performance (Y). The results of the direct influence test are presented in Table 3 below.

Results of Direct Influence Hypothesis Test

Table 3. Direct Influence Test

Variable	T Statistics	P Values	Results
Competence (X1) → Performance (Y)	7.143	0.011	H1 Accepted
Personal Characteristics (X2) → Performance (Y)	3.496	0.012	H1 Accepted

Based on table 3, it can be seen that all independent variables individually have a significant influence. This is evidenced by the level of significance of the competency variable (X1), personal characteristics (X2) on teacher performance (Y), having a significance level below 0.05. The competency variable (X1) on Performance (Y) has a T Statistic value of 7.143 with a significance level of 0.011. While the Personal Characteristics variable (X2) on Performance (Y) has a T Statistic value of 3.946 with a significance level of 0.012.

2020; Pinca, 2015; Rande, 2016; & Fariz, 2020), (Fatmah, 2017), (Purwanto & Soliha, 2017), (Anggriawan et al., 2023), (Rahim et al., 2017), (Supriadi et al., 2018), (Parashakti et al., 2020), (Indarti, 2018), (Mustikawati & Qomariah, 2020), (Putra et al., 2020), (Siagian, 2018), (Mulyani & Saputri, 2019), (Dewanti & Artaya, 2019), (Fajduani et al., 2021), (Arif et al., 2021), (Permanasari et al., 2014), (Novita & Yulianti, 2020), (Azizah et al., 2022), (Herawati & Mahfudnurnajamuddin, 2018), (Abdi & Wahid, 2017), (Pujiarti, 2019), (Sholehatusya'diah, 2017), (Prahastyo et al., 2024), (Hendrawan & Sanosra, 2023), (Irawan et al., 2024), (Galih et al., 2023), (Qomariah & Utamy, 2023), (A. Setiawan et al., 2023), (Rahmadani et al., 2020), (Rusmayanti et al., 2022), (Qomariah et al., 2023), (Hapsari et al., 2022), (Puspitasari et al., 2024) (Askany et al., 2024), (Y. Setiawan et al., 2022), which states that competence has a significant influence on performance. Meanwhile, research that is not in line with this research which states that competence has no impact on performance is conducted by (Kurniawan et al., 2021), (Utomo et al., 2019).

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Competence on Performance

After testing and analyzing the data, the results obtained stated that Competence has a significant influence on Performance. In other words, high competence will improve a teacher's performance. This is because high competence can encourage teachers to work more precisely, so that they can make teaching and learning time more effective and efficient. So it can be concluded that the third hypothesis is accepted. These results support research conducted by (Abusama et al., 2017), (Marhayani et al., 2019), (Renyut et al., 2017), (Kotamena et al., 2020), (Adam & Kamase, 2019; Amdani et al., 2019; Basalamah, 2017; Friolina et al., 2017; Indiyarningsih et al., 2020; Nyoto et al.,

The Influence of Personal Characteristics on Performance

After testing and analyzing the data, the results obtained stated that Personal Characteristics have a

significant influence on Performance. This is because good Personal Characteristics will make it easier for students to absorb the knowledge conveyed by a teacher, increase togetherness, and create a sense of mutual respect for each other. In other words, good Personal Characteristics will encourage increased Performance. So it can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis is accepted. These results support research conducted by (Sihombing et al., 2018), (Hajati et al., 2018), (Ramdhani & Sridadi, 2019) which states that characteristics have a significant influence on performance.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the discussion that has been presented, several things can be concluded as answers to the problems raised in this study. First, hypothesis testing shows a positive and significant influence of competency variables on performance. Second, hypothesis testing also proves that personal characteristic variables have a positive and significant influence on performance.

Based on the results of the study and conclusions, the following suggestions can be made: a) For the Research Object, the results of the study show that the Personal Characteristics variable on Performance has the lowest level of significance compared to other variables. This indicates that the Personal Characteristics variable still needs special attention in order to improve a teacher's performance. b) It is hoped that further research will be expanded by adding other variables related to things that affect the improvement of Teacher Performance. such as: work environment, incentives, curriculum, etc..

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